

DEVELOPMENT OF ORANGE PEEL–INFUSED VIRGIN COCONUT OIL SERUM: A NATURAL APPROACH FOR DERMATOLOGICAL CARE

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ABSTRACT

An enriched oil serum was formulated by cold infusion of shade-dried orange peel (*Citrus sinensis*) into virgin coconut oil (VCO) using a two-stage infusion method. The product exhibited a golden-yellow colour, pleasant citrus aroma, and smooth, non-sticky texture. Phytochemical screening revealed the presence of flavonoids, tannins, phenolic compounds, alkaloids, saponins, essential oils, and vitamin C. The oil showed favourable physicochemical properties like specific gravity 0.921 (25 °C), refractive index 1.449, acid value 1.2, peroxide value 0.9 meq/kg, and saponification value 262. Stability testing confirmed resistance to rancidity, colour change, and phase separation under thermal, light, and storage conditions. In a volunteer study (n = 5, aged 20–45 years, 30 days daily use), improvements were reported in skin softness (93%), glow/brightness (80%), and mild acne reduction (80%), with no irritation observed. The combination of VCO's lauric

acid and orange peel's bio actives, such as hesperidin, d-limonene, and ascorbic acid, offers antioxidant, antimicrobial, and skin-brightening effects. This eco-friendly, cost-effective formulation demonstrates potential as a multifunctional cosmeceutical for daily skincare.

KEYWORDS: Orange peel, cold maceration, virgin coconut oil, antioxidant, skin-brightening, phytochemicals, cosmeceutical formulation.

INTRODUCTION

Herbal Oil: Herbal oils are natural preparations obtained by infusing medicinal plants or their parts (leaves, roots, flowers, peels) into a base oil, allowing the extraction of active phytochemicals. These oils serve as potent therapeutic agents, combining the medicinal benefits of both the carrier oil and the herbal ingredients.

Traditionally used in Ayurveda, Siddha, Unani, and other folk medicinal systems, herbal oils have been applied for centuries in the management of skincare, skin disorders, pain relief, wound healing, inflammation, and hair care. With the growing global interest in natural, eco-friendly, and sustainable skincare, herbal oils have regained prominence as cosmeceutical agents, offering benefits like moisturization, antioxidant protection, antimicrobial action, and anti-aging effects.

Commonly used carrier oils include coconut oil, sesame oil, olive oil, and jojoba oil, which possess their own therapeutic properties. These oils act as solvents to extract fat-soluble phytoconstituents such as flavonoids, terpenoids, essential oils, and vitamins, enhancing the penetration of actives into deeper layers of the skin.

The preparation of herbal oils involves various infusion methods like cold maceration, hot infusion, or solar infusion, depending on the sensitivity of the active ingredients. The resulting herbal oil can be used directly or formulated into ointments, creams, balms, or massage oils.

Thus, herbal oils represent a bridge between traditional knowledge and modern skincare science, offering safe, effective, and holistic alternatives to synthetic products.^[1-6]

Orange and Orange Peel (*Citrus sinensis*)

Fig: 01 Orange Peel.

Orange (*Citrus sinensis*) is a widely consumed citrus fruit known for its refreshing flavour, high vitamin C content, and numerous health benefits. Belonging to the family Rutaceae, oranges are cultivated extensively across the world, particularly in tropical and subtropical

regions. While the pulp is used for juice and culinary purposes, the peel, often considered waste, is a rich source of bioactive compounds with potent therapeutic and cosmetic value.

The orange peel contains a diverse array of phytochemicals, including flavonoids (like hesperidin, naringin), essential oils (notably d-limonene), vitamin C, carotenoids, and polyphenols, which possess antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, skin-brightening, and anti-aging properties. These compounds help neutralize oxidative stress, lighten hyperpigmentation, stimulate collagen production, and improve overall skin tone and texture.

In traditional and modern herbal practices, orange peel has been used in face masks, scrubs, bath soaks, and increasingly in infused oils and serums for skincare. Its pleasant citrus aroma and skin-enhancing benefits make it a valuable natural ingredient in cosmeceuticals and aromatherapy.

The transformation of orange peel waste into functional skincare products not only promotes sustainability and green chemistry, but also adds value to agricultural byproducts, aligning with eco-conscious consumer trends.^[7-13]

Virgin Coconut Oil (*Cocos nucifera* L.)

Fig: 02 Coconut Oil.

Virgin coconut oil is a natural, unrefined oil extracted from the fresh and mature kernel of the coconut (*Cocos nucifera* L.) by mechanical or natural means without the application of high heat or chemical refining. Unlike regular coconut oil, Virgin coconut oil retains its natural aroma, flavour, and a rich profile of bioactive compounds, making it a premium-grade oil for medicinal, cosmetic, and nutritional use.

Virgin coconut oil is primarily composed of medium-chain fatty acids (MCFAs) such as lauric acid, capric acid, and caprylic acid, which exhibit antimicrobial, antiviral, and antifungal properties. Among these, lauric acid (about 50%) is known for its ability to disrupt

lipid membranes of pathogens, making Virgin coconut oil a potent natural remedy for skin infections and inflammation.

In traditional medicine systems like Ayurveda and Filipino folk practices, virgin coconut oil has been used for wound healing, skin hydration, scalp health, and anti-aging applications. Its emollient and occlusive properties help in restoring the skin barrier, reducing trans epidermal water loss, and improving skin elasticity.

Virgin coconut oil is also a widely accepted carrier oil in herbal infusions, as it efficiently extracts and preserves lipophilic phytoconstituents like terpenoids, flavonoids, carotenoids, and essential oils from plant materials. This makes it especially valuable in the formulation of herbal cosmetics, balms, creams, and infused oils or serums.

The rising demand for natural, chemical-free, and sustainable beauty products has further propelled the popularity of virgin coconut oil in the global cosmeceutical and wellness industries.

Infusion

Infusion is a traditional and widely practiced method of extracting bioactive compounds from plant materials by soaking them in a suitable solvent over a period of time. This gentle extraction technique allows the transfer of phytochemicals—such as flavonoids, essential oils, alkaloids, tannins, and vitamins—into carriers like water, oil, alcohol, or glycerine, depending on the intended use.

In cosmetic and herbal oil preparations, infusion in oils (called oil infusion) is especially popular. It involves soaking dried or fresh plant material—such as flowers, peels, leaves, or roots—into a carrier oil like virgin coconut oil, olive oil, or jojoba oil. This process facilitates the extraction of fat-soluble components, including terpenoids, carotenoids, and essential oils. Infusion is widely used to transfer therapeutic plant compounds into carrier oils (e.g., coconut oil) for use in skincare, skin nourishment, healing, and rejuvenation, haircare, or medicinal formulations.^[19-22]

Infusion can be carried out using different techniques.

Table 01: Types of infusion process.

S.no	Type	Description	Used For
01	Cold Infusion	Plant material is soaked in oil or water at room temperature for several days (usually 1–2 weeks).	Heat-sensitive compounds like vitamin C, essential oils
02	Hot Infusion	Plant material is heated gently in oil using a double boiler or water bath for a few hours.	Faster extraction, suitable for tough plant parts
03	Solar Infusion	The mixture is kept in sunlight (usually in a glass jar) for 1–2 weeks.	Traditional herbal preparations
04	Aqueous Infusion	Plant parts are steeped in hot water (like making tea), typically for soft tissues like leaves or flowers.	Herbal teas and mild skin washes
05	Alcoholic Infusion (Tinctures)	Plant material is infused in alcohol for several days or weeks.	Stronger solvent for alkaloids, resins
06	Oil Infusion	Herbs or peels are soaked in oils (like coconut, olive, jojoba) to extract fat-soluble compounds.	Skincare oils, massage oils, ointments

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Virgin Coconut Oil (VCO): Cold-pressed, unrefined, and locally sourced.

- A common carrier oil in herbal formulations, coconut oil is celebrated for its deep penetration and moisturizing properties. It helps reduce protein loss in hair, preventing damage and dryness.

Benefits: Antimicrobial, moisturizing, and promotes skin health.

Orange Peel (*Citrus sinensis*): Fresh sweet orange peels, shade-dried for 7–10 days and powdered.

The orange peel is high in certain phytochemicals, flavonoids, and other antioxidants, as well as providing vitamin A, B, C, copper, calcium, and magnesium.

Glassware & Equipment

Amber bottles, muslin cloth, pycnometer, refractometer, magnetic stirrer **Chemicals and reagents for phytochemical screening:** Methanol, ethanol, hydrochloric acid, ferric chloride, magnesium ribbon, ammonia, chloroform, sulphuric acid, etc.

Preparation of Orange Peel-Infused Coconut Oil Serum

Drying of Orange Peel

- Fresh orange peels were washed thoroughly and peel it and peeled and shade-dried for 7–10 days.
- Dried peels stored in airtight containers.

2.2 Infusion Method (Cold Infusion)

- **Stage 1:** 100 g of dried orange peel was added to 700 ml of virgin coconut oil in a sterile, Glass jar.
- The mixture was kept at room temperature (25–28°C) for **15 days**, with daily manual shaking to enhance infusion.
- After 15 days, the mixture was filtered using muslin cloth to remove peel residue.
- **Stage 2 (Double Enrichment):** Another 100 g of fresh dried peel was added to the previously filtered oil and infused for an additional **15 days**.
- Final filtration was done, and the infused oil serum was stored in dispense bottles at room temperature.

Fig 03: Stage 1 & Stage 2 Infusion process.

Evaluation of Oil Properties

Different types of Categorized Test along with Procedure and Observed results

S.No	Category	Test	Description / Procedure	Expected Result	Observed Results
1	Organoleptic Properties	Colour	Visual observation under daylight.	Golden yellow to pale yellow.	Golden yellow colour
		Odor	Smelled directly to assess aroma.	Pleasant citrus or orange aroma	orange aroma
		Consistency/Texture	Rubbed between fingers to evaluate oiliness and spreadability.	Smooth, light, non-sticky.	Smooth, non-sticky
		Appearance	Observed in a transparent glass container.	Clear, non-turbid.	Clear, non-turbid liquid
	Specific Gravity	Specific Gravity	Measured using a pycnometer and compared with water.	~0.91–0.93 (for coconut oil)	0.921(25 °C)
		Refractive Index	1–2 drops on Abbe refractometer, measured at 40°C.	~1.448–1.450	1.449
		Acid Value	Titration with 0.1N KOH after dissolving oil in ethanol and adding phenolphthalein.	≤1.5 (low free fatty acids)	1.2
		Peroxide Value	Measured by iodometric titration to assess rancidity.	<10 meq/kg	0.9
		Saponification Value	Reflux with alcoholic KOH, titrate excess KOH to determine average molecular weight of fatty acids.	250–265 (for coconut oil)	262
	3	Stability Studies	Thermal Stability	Stored at 40°C for 7–14 days in incubator; checked for odour, consistency, and phase separation.	No foul smell or separation
Light Stability			Exposed to sunlight for 7 days; observed for discoloration or rancidity.	Colour remains stable	No discoloration or odour observed
Storage Stability			Stored at room temperature and 4°C for 30 days;	No separation or odour observed	No changes in consistency, odour, or phase

			observed for precipitation, odour, and consistency.		separation were observed
4	Phytochemical Screening	Flavonoids	Shinoda Test: Mg ribbon + conc. HCl + extract → pink/red colour.	Flavonoids present	Present
		Phenolic Compounds	Ferric chloride (5%) + extract → blue/violet colour.	Phenols present	Present
		Tannins	Ferric chloride + extract → greenish-blue/black colour.	Tannins present	Present
		Alkaloids	Mayer's/ Dragendorff's reagent → cream/brown precipitate.	Alkaloids present	Present
		Saponins	Shake with water → persistent foam after 10 min.	Saponins present	Present
		Terpenoids	Salkowski test: extract + chloroform + conc. H ₂ SO ₄ → reddish-brown ring at interface.	Terpenoids present	Absent
		Essential Oils	Spot test or steam distillation → translucent non-greasy spot/aroma.	Essential oils confirmed	Present
		Vitamin C (Ascorbic Acid)	DCPIP test: extract titrated with 0.1% DCPIP → blue colour turns colourless.	Ascorbic acid present	Present

User Feedback (Volunteer Study)

- **Sample size:** Fifteen volunteers (aged 20–45 years)
- **Duration:** 30 days of daily night-time use
- To assess the consumer acceptability and effectiveness of the prepared *Orange Peel-Infused Coconut Oil Serum*, a volunteer study was conducted. A total of 15 healthy volunteers (aged 20–45 years) participated in the study after obtaining informed consent. Each volunteer was instructed to apply the serum once daily at night for one month on a cleansed face and neck area.

- Feedback was collected using a structured questionnaire evaluating key parameters such as fragrance, texture, ease of application, absorption, non-greasiness, skin smoothness, moisturization, and overall satisfaction.

Parameter	Excellent	Good	Fair	Poor
Fragrance	10	4	1	0
Texture	9	6	0	0
Absorption	9	6	0	0
Non-greasiness	8	7	0	0
Skin smoothness	11	4	0	0
Moisturization	12	3	0	0
Overall satisfaction	13	2	0	0

Parameters Observed

- Skin softness improvement: 93%
- Mild acne reduction: 80%
- No irritation or allergic reactions: 100%
- Glow/brightness improvement: 80%

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After one month of regular night-time application, volunteers reported noticeable improvement in skin texture, softness, and radiance. The serum was easily absorbed without leaving a greasy residue and imparted a pleasant natural fragrance. No signs of irritation, redness, or discomfort were observed during the study period. The overall feedback indicated that the formulation was well accepted and suitable for daily skincare use.

4. DISCUSSION

The results clearly demonstrate that the two-stage cold infusion method effectively extracted and preserved heat-sensitive phytoconstituents such as flavonoids, phenolics, and vitamin C from orange peel. The formulation's golden-yellow colour and characteristic fragrance confirm successful transfer of essential oils and bio-actives into the oil phase.

The synergistic combination of orange peel phytochemicals (hesperidin, d-limonene, ascorbic acid) and virgin coconut oil fatty acids (notably lauric acid) offers multiple dermatological benefits. Hesperidin and ascorbic acid provide antioxidant and tyrosinase-inhibitory activity, helping to reduce pigmentation and promote even skin tone. Meanwhile, lauric acid contributes antimicrobial and emollient effects, supporting skin barrier repair, hydration, and protection from microbial infections.

The phytochemical and physicochemical findings correlated strongly with the volunteer study outcomes, indicating both efficacy and safety. Improvements in skin softness, radiance, and mild acne reduction suggest that the formulation promotes healthy skin rejuvenation. The absence of irritation further supports its biocompatibility for daily topical use.

Overall, the findings confirm that orange peel–infused virgin coconut oil serum is a stable, bioactive-rich, and multifunctional formulation with potential applications as a natural cosmeceutical for skincare. Its eco-friendly preparation and utilization of fruit peel waste align with sustainability and green chemistry principles.

CONCLUSION

The present study successfully formulated and evaluated an orange peel–infused virgin coconut oil serum using a staged cold-infusion technique. The method preserved key bioactive constituents—including flavonoids, phenolics, essential oils, and vitamin C—and produced a stable, fragrant, and skin-compatible product.

Physicochemical and stability assessments confirmed that the formulation met quality and safety standards, while phytochemical screening verified the presence of compounds responsible for antioxidant, antimicrobial, and skin-brightening effects. Volunteer feedback further validated its effectiveness and acceptability, with noticeable improvements in skin softness, radiance, and texture.

The combined properties of orange peel bio-actives and virgin coconut oil resulted in a synergistic, multifunctional cosmeceutical suitable for regular skincare. Moreover, the use of fruit peel waste emphasizes a sustainable, cost-effective, and environmentally friendly approach, supporting the global shift toward green and natural skincare solutions.

Future studies involving larger, placebo-controlled clinical trials, antioxidant quantification, and long-term stability assessments are recommended to further substantiate the product's efficacy, safety, and commercial potential in the cosmetic and pharmaceutical industries.

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